

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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TURNkey

Deliverable D3.3

Online service for the rapid estimation of shaking using citizen information from smartphone apps (EEW)

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29/09/2020	1.0	Final Draft	Final

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

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LINKS

This deliverable lists the associated online services that give access to data and to their products.

- All EMSC felt reports data are available via a webservice hosted on the Seismic Portal, the EMSC website for seismologists (real time exchange of felt reports will be developed later in the project within Task 6.2):
<https://www.seismicportal.eu/testimonies-ws/>
- Further products as e.g. the spatial distribution of felt reports, intensity-distance curves and doughnut figures are computed and accessible on the event page for felt earthquakes (in the "Maps" section):
<https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/felt.php>